

γ , γ -Disubstituted Itaconic Acids. Part VIII. The Stobbe Condensation of 6-Aroyl Tetralins with Succinic Ester

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6-*p*-Toluyyl, 6-*p*-chlorobenzoyl, and 6-*p*-bromobenzoyl tetralins condense with succinic ester in the presence of potassium *t*-butoxide, to give the *trans*-(*p*-tolyl/CO₂Et) half-ester in the first case, and a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-(*p*-Cl-C₆H₄/CO₂Et) and (*p*-Br-C₆H₄/CO₂Et) half-esters in the last two cases. The *cis*- and *trans*-half esters are cyclised to give finally phenyl-phenanthrene and 1,2'-binaphthyl derivatives, respectively. The corresponding diacids on the other hand are cyclised to dibenzofluorenone derivatives.

6-*p*-TOLUYL, 6-*p*-chlorobenzoyl, and 6-*p*-bromobenzoyl tetralins were prepared by Friedel-Crafts condensation of *p*-toluyyl, *p*-chlorobenzoyl and *p*-bromobenzoyl chlorides with tetralin, respectively.

Stobbe Condensation of 6-Toluyyl Tetralin (1; R' = Me) (cf. Scheme). This ketone was condensed with diethyl succinate in the presence of potassium *t*-butoxide to give the *trans*-(*p*-tolyl/CO₂Et) 3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-(6-tetralyl)-4-*p*-tolyl-but-3-enoic acid (2; R' = Me) in 80% yield, which upon oxidation with potassium permanganate afforded the original ketone. The *trans*-(*p*-tolyl/CO₂Et) relationship was revealed by converting the product into a tetralylnaphthalene derivative (4). Thus, cyclisation of compound (2; R¹ = Me) with sodium acetate in acetic anhydride gave 4-acetoxy-6-methyl-1-(6-tetralyl)-2-naphthoate (4a; R¹ = Me). This upon saponification afforded the hydroxy acid (4b; R¹ = Me). Methylation of this hydroxy acid with dimethyl sulphate and potassium carbonate gave the methoxy ester (4c; R¹ = Me). Its tetralylnaphthalene structure is substantiated by its u.v. spectrum (cf. Table 4). Subsequent saponification of the preceding methoxy ester gave the methoxy acid (4d; R¹ = Me), which on decarboxylation with copper-bronze in quinoline gave 4-methoxy-6-methyl-1-(6-tetralyl)-naphthalene (4e; R¹ = Me).

The i.r. spectrum of the latter compound shows a very strong band at 825 cm⁻¹ and a medium band at 895 cm⁻¹ characteristic of out-of-plane bending frequencies of two adjacent and one aromatic hydrogen, atoms respectively². This supports the binaphthyl and not the phenanthrene structure, since

the i.r. spectrum of the latter must show one band only for two adjacent hydrogen atoms. The structure assigned to this compound was also inferred from the fact that on dehydrogenation with selenium metal it afforded 4-methoxy-6-methyl-1,2'-binaphthyl (5e; R¹ = Me). The structure of the latter compound is supported by its electronic spectrum which shows two maxima at 215 nm (ϵ 78,230) and 305 nm (ϵ 14,080), which indicates its similarity to 1,2'-binaphthyl [λ_{max} 222 nm (ϵ 56,230), and λ_{max} 297 nm (ϵ 14,450)]³, (cf. Table 4). Cyclisation of the methoxy acid (4d; R¹ = Me) with phosphorus pentoxide in dry benzene gave the tetrahydrodibenzofluorenone (11c; R¹ = Me).

Stobbe Condensation of p-Chlorobenzoyl Tetralin (1, R¹ = Cl). When this ketone was condensed with diethyl succinate as usual, it gave a semi-solid mixture of half-esters in 72% yield. This mixture (14.5g) was separated by trituration with *n*-hexane and ether to a soluble fraction (A) (9g) and an insoluble fraction (B) (5.5g). The former was proved to be *trans*-(*p*-Cl-C₆H₄/CO₂Et)-4-*p*-chlorophenyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-(6-tetralyl)-but-3-enoic acid (2; R¹ = Cl), whereas the latter was the corresponding *cis*-half-ester (3; R¹ = Cl). Each half-ester gave the original ketone on oxidation. The ratio of *cis*- to *trans*-half-esters estimated by fractional crystallisation was about (2:3). This result was found to be in a fairly good agreement with the relative proportion of the two isomers determined by electronic spectroscopy (cf. experimental). The configuration of the *trans*-half-ester was established by subjecting it to the above series of reactions to give the tetralyl-naphthalene derivatives (4a, b, c, d; R¹ = Cl). The tetralyl-naphthalene structure was inferred from the following evidence: (a) the electronic spectrum of 6-chloro-4-hydroxy-1-(6-tetra-

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yl)-2-naphthoic acid (4b; $R^1 = Cl$) shows absorption bands at 250 and 315 nm (ϵ 35,400 and 6,130, respectively), which are very similar to those observed in the spectrum of 4-hydroxy-1-(6-tetralyl)-2-naphthoic acid and stand for 1B_b and 1L_a bands of aromatic compounds (cf Table 4). (b) Decarboxylation of the methoxynaphthoic acid (4d; $R = Cl$) gave 6-chloro-4-methoxy-1-(6-tetralyl)-naphthalene. Its i.r. spectrum shows a very strong band at 825 cm^{-1} and a medium band at 890 cm^{-1} , characteristic of the out-of-plane bending frequencies (γ C-H) of two adjacent and one aromatic hydrogen atoms², respectively. (c) Dehydrogenation of the tetralyl-naphthalene (4e; $R^1 = Cl$), gave 6-chloro-4-methoxy-1, 2'-binaphthyl (5e; $R^1 = Cl$). Its electronic spectrum shows two maxima at 219 nm (ϵ 68,040) and 307.5 nm (ϵ 13,610) almost identical with that of 1, 2'-binaphthyl, obtained by the same route from 6-benzoyl-tetralin³, and which stand for the 1B_b and 1L_a bands of aromatic compounds. (d) When the methoxy ester (4c; $R^1 = Cl$) was heated with palladised charcoal it was dechlorinated, dehydrogenated and hydrolysed in one step, to give 4-methoxy-1-(2'-naphthyl)-2-naphthoic acid (5d; $R^1 = H$); un-depressed when admixed with an authentic sample.³

Cyclisation of the methoxy acid (4d; $R^1 = Cl$) with phosphorus pentoxide in dry benzene gave the tetrahydrodibenzofluorenone (11c; $R^1 = Cl$).

The *cis*-half-ester, on the other hand, when subjected to the same series of reactions gave the tetrahydrophenanthrene derivatives (6a, b, c, d; $R^1 = Cl$). The phenylphenanthrene structure assigned to these compounds was inferred from the following evidences: (a) The electronic spectra of methyl 1-*p*-chlorophenyl-5, 6, 7, 8-tetrahydro-4-methoxyphenanthrene-2-carboxylate (6c; $R^1 = Cl$) and the corresponding acid (6d; $R^1 = Cl$) are very similar to those of methyl 5, 6, 7, 8-tetrahydro-4-methylphenanthrene-2-carboxylate,³ (b) Decarboxylation of the methoxy acid (6d; $R^1 = Cl$) gave 1-*p*-chlorophenyl-5, 6, 7, 8-tetrahydro-4-methoxyphenanthrene (6e; $R^1 = Cl$). Its i.r. spectrum shows a strong band at 820 cm^{-1} , characteristic of γ C-H of two adjacent hydrogen atoms. (c) Dehydrogenation of the tetrahydrophenanthrene (6e; $R^1 = Cl$) gave 1-*p*-chlorophenyl-4-methoxyphenanthrene (7e; $R^1 = Cl$). Its electronic spectrum is similar to those of 4-methoxy-1-phenylphenanthrene,³ and 4-phenylphenanthrene⁴, (cf. Table 4). (d) When the methoxy ester (6c; $R^1 = Cl$) was heated with palladium charcoal, dechlorination, accompanied by dehydrogenation and hydrolysis occurred to give 4-methoxy-1-phenylphenanthrene-2-carboxylic acid (7d; $R^1 = H$), identical with an authentic sample.³ Its i.r. spectrum shows strong bands at 750 cm^{-1} and 707 cm^{-1} , and at 1705 cm^{-1} characteristic of γ C-H of 5 adjacent aromatic H-atoms,² and ν C=O of aromatic acids,⁵ respectively. The formation of tetrahydrophenanthrene derivative (6a; $R^1 = Cl$) rather than the isomeric tetrahydroanthracene derivative by the cyclisation of *cis*-(*p*-Cl-C₆H₄/CO₂Et)-half-ester (3; $R^1 = Cl$) is attributed to the higher contribution of Kekule structure of ring-A to the actual state of the molecule,⁶ i.e. the bond between carbon atoms 1 and 2 has more

double-bond character than that between carbon atoms 2 and 3.

Stobbe Condensation of 6-p-Bromobenzoyl Tetralin (1; $R^1 = Br$). This was condensed with diethyl succinate as usual to give a semisolid mixture of half-esters in about 65% yield. This mixture (28.8 g) was separated to *cis*-(*p*-Br-C₆H₄/CO₂Et)-4-*p*-bromophenyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-(6-tetralyl)-but-3-enoic acid (3; $R^1 = Br$) (9.4 g) and the *trans*-isomeric half ester (2; $R^1 = Br$) (19.4 g) (see experimental). The diarylidene structure of the two half-esters followed from their oxidation to the original ketone. The ratio of the *cis*- to the *trans*-(*p*-Br C₆H₄/CO₂Et)-half-ester, estimated by fractional crystallisation or by electronic spectroscopy was found to be 1:2, respectively (see experimental). The *trans*-half-ester was configured by subjecting it to the above series of reactions to give the tetralynaphthalene derivatives (4a, b, c; $R^1 = Br$). The tetralynaphthalene structure of these compounds was inferred from the following evidence: (a) The u.v. spectrum of the hydroxy acid (4b; $R^1 = Br$) (see Table 4) is very similar to that of 4-hydroxy-1-(6-tetralyl)-2-naphthoic acid,³ (b) when the methoxy ester was heated with palladised charcoal, debromination and dehydrogenation accompanied by hydrolysis occurred simultaneously to give 4-methoxy-1-(2'-naphthyl)-naphthoic acid (5d; $R^1 = H$), identical with an authentic sample.³ The *cis*-half-ester was configured by subjecting it to the same series of reactions to give the tetrahydrophenanthrene derivatives (6a, b, c; $R^1 = Br$). The tetrahydrophenanthrene structure assigned to these compounds was established by: (a) the identity of u.v. spectra of these compounds with their corresponding chloroisomers, and (b) when the methoxy ester (6c; $R^1 = Br$) was heated with palladised charcoal it gave 4-methoxy-1-phenylphenanthrene-2-carboxylic acid (7d; $R^1 = Br$) identical with an authentic sample.³

Synthesis of Oxindenylic acids (10) and Dibenzofluorenones (11). Saponification of the half-esters (2; $R^1 = Me$) and (2; $R^1 = Cl$) gave the corresponding dibasic acids, which have the same geometrical configuration as their half-esters, since they were converted by series of reactions (cf. scheme) into the same dibenzofluorenones (11c; $R^1 = Me$) and (11; $R^1 = Cl$), obtained by the cyclisation of (4d; $R^1 = Me$ and Cl, respectively). The dibasic acids (8; $R^1 = Me$) and (8; $R^1 = Cl$) were dehydrated by acetyl chloride to their anhydrides (9; $R^1 = Me$) and (9; $R^1 = Cl$), which failed to solidify, and were directly treated with anhydrous aluminium chloride in nitrobenzene to give (6, 7, 8, 9-tetrahydro-1-oxo-3-*p*-tolyl (10; $R^1 = Me$) and 3-*p*-chlorophenyl (10; $R^1 = Cl$) benz[e]inden-2-yl) acetic acid, respectively. The structure assigned to the latter compounds was based on the following evidences: (a) Their orange colour, which is reflected in the appearance of a low intensity absorption band in the visible region ($n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition) (cf. Table 6), (b) formation of 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazones, and (c) their i.r. spectra, which show strong bands characteristic of ν C=O of aliphatic acids,^{5a} and α, β -unsaturated five membered cyclic aryl ketones,^{5b} and

a medium band at 845 cm^{-1} , characteristic of out-of-plane bending frequency for two adjacent aromatic hydrogen atoms,² (cf. Table 5). The cyclisation at position 5 rather than position 7 of the tetralyl nucleus is attributed to the fixation of the double bond in the tetralin nucleus.⁶

The oxoindenylic acids (10; $R^1 = \text{Me}$) and (10; $R^1 = \text{Cl}$) were further cyclised using sodium acetate in acetic anhydride to give 11-acetoxy-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydro-9-methyl- (11a; $R^1 = \text{Me}$) and 9-chloro- (11a; $R^1 = \text{Cl}$)-13H-dibenzo [a, g] fluorenyl-13-one, respectively in high yields. Saponification

followed by methylation gave the corresponding dibenzofluorenones (11c; R¹ = Me) and (11c; R¹ = Cl), respectively.

The conversion of the half-esters (2; R¹ = Me) and (2; R¹ = Cl) and their corresponding dibasic acids into the same dibenzofluorenones (11c; R¹ = Me) and (11c; R¹ = Cl), respectively, by two different routes indicated that the two compounds have the same stereochemical configuration and no isomerisation occurred during hydrolysis.

Interpretation of the Relative Proportion of Stereoisomers. It has been suggested by Baddar *et al.*^{3,8} that the ratio of the stereoisomeric half-esters produced in the Stobbe condensation, is largely determined by steric and/or polar non-bonded interaction involved in the formation of the intermediate diastereomeric lactones of the type (12) and (13). In a study of the condensation involving aryl isopropyl ketones,⁸ it was concluded that the formation of the *trans*-(Ar/CO₂Et) intermediate [type (12)] is favoured by repulsive forces between the negative field of the carbonyl oxygen in the ester group and the π-cloud of the aromatic ring when the latter is phenyl or *p*-anisyl; whereas attractive or less repulsive forces favour the *cis*-(Ar/CO₂Et) intermediate [type (13)] when the aryl group is positively polarised by an electron-attracting substituent such as a chlorine atom.

The formation of the two paraconic esters (12) and (13) arise from the attack of the carbonyl group by the initially formed carbanion derived from succinic ester either by a two step mechanism as reported by Johnson *et al.*⁹ or by one step mechanism (concerted mechanism).

Carbanions which are not stabilised by resonance seem likely to possess an sp³ hybridised structure (14) with the unshared pair occupying the apex of the tetrahedron, i.e. structure identical to that of amines.

However, it is believed that the umbrella effect exists here so that the unshared pair and the central carbon rapidly oscillate from one side of the plane to the other.¹⁰ However, carbanions in which the negative charge is stabilised by resonance involving overlap of the unshared pair orbital with the π-elec-

trons of a multiple bond (in this case the C = O) are essentially planar, though unsymmetrical solvation or ion-pairing effects may cause the structure to deviate from true planarity.¹¹ If the formed carbanion is, therefore, planar the two paraconic acids may arise as a result of attack of the carbonyl group by the carbanion from both sides. However, in *t*-butyl alcohol, the carbanion is probably closely associated with its cation and solvation through hydrogen bonds at the front side. Abstraction of hydrogen from hydrogen-bonded solvent molecules is very likely to give products of retained configuration.¹² Since the carbanion formed by the action of K⁺O⁻C(CH₃)₃ in *t*-butanol probably occurs in the solvated form (15) and (16),¹² then it is more likely that they may attack the carbonyl group of the ketone by their back side to give two paraconic esters (12) and (13). The ratio of these esters is determined by steric factors and/or polar non-bonded interactions existing between the groups attached to the carbonyl group of the ketone and the carbanion

The results of this investigation show beyond doubt that polar non-bonded interaction are more effective than steric factors. Thus, whereas the condensation of phenyl 6-tetralyl ketone with diethyl succinate gave a mixture of two isomeric half-esters (2; R¹ = H) and (3; R¹ = H) in the ratio 3 : 2, respectively, the condensation of 6-*p*-toluyl tetralin, 6-*p*-chlorobenzoyl- and 6-*p*-bromobenzoyl tetralin gave the *trans*-(Ar/CO₂Et)-half-ester in the former case, and a mixture of the *trans*- and *cis*-(Ar/CO₂Et)-half esters in the latter cases (cf. Table 1).

This result could not be explained on the basis of steric effect, but can be easily interpreted if we take into consideration the polar non-bonded interaction between the carbonyl group of the ethoxycarbonyl group and the substituted phenyl group.

According to the polar non-bonded interaction between the eclipsed groups, the paraconic ester with

the least repulsion between the negatively polarised carbonyl group and the substituted phenyl group will be formed in greater proportion. Since the *p*-tolyl group carries a much higher electron-density

chloride (0.2 mole) heated at 50° for 3 hr and worked up as usual. 6-*p*-Tolyl tetralin was obtained as colourless crystals (18.5 g), m.p. 61-62° (from methanol) (Found: C, 86.7; H, 7.4. C₁₈H₁₈O requires: C, 86.4; H, 7.3%). Its D.N.P. (red) had m.p. 194-5° (from benzene) (Found: C, 67.3; H, 5.3; N, 13.4. C₂₄H₂₂O₄N₄ requires: C, 67.0; H, 5.2; N, 13.0%). 6-*p*-Chlorobenzoyl tetralin (18.1 g, colourless) had m.p. 86° (from methanol) (Found, C, 75.1; H, 5.4; Cl, 13.2. C₁₇H₁₅OCl requires: C, 75.3; H, 5.6; Cl, 13.1%). Its D.N.P. (red) had m.p. 243° (from methanol) (Found: C, 61.0; H, 4.3; Cl, 7.8; N, 12.6. C₂₃H₁₉O₄ClN₄ requires: C, 61.3; H, 4.2; Cl, 7.9; N, 12.4%). 6-*p*-Bromobenzoyl tetralin (19.2, colourless) had m.p. 99-100° (from methanol) Found: C, 65.2; H, 4.9; Br, 25.7. C₁₇H₁₅OBr requires: C, 64.8; H, 4.8; Br, 25.4%). Its D.N.P. (red) had m.p. 268-9° (from ethanol) (Found: N, 11.6. C₂₃H₁₉O₄BrN₄ requires: N, 11.3%).

Table 1

Ketone	Total yield	trans-	cis-
		(Ar*/CO ₂ Et) (2)	(Ar*/CO ₂ Et) (3)
6- <i>p</i> -Tolyl tetralin <i>a</i>	80%	100%	—
6- <i>p</i> -Chlorobenzoyltetralin	72%	60%	40%
6- <i>p</i> -Bromobenzoyltetralin	65%	66%	34%

*Ar = *p*-Substituted phenyl

than the *p*-chloro- or *p*-bromophenyl groups owing to the electron-releasing property of the methyl group, one should expect that the isomer in which the *p*-tolyl and ethoxycarbonyl are *cis*- to each other, i.e. paraconic ester (17) should be less readily formed than that in which the *p*-chloro- or *p*-bromophenyl are *cis*- to the same group. The formation of the *cis*-(*p*-C₆H₄Cl/CO₂Et)-half-ester (3; R¹ = Cl) in a slightly greater proportion than the *cis*-(*p*-C₆H₄Br/CO₂Et)-half-ester (3; R¹ = Br) may be attributed to the fact that the chlorine atom has a high -I effect and thus the electron density on the *p*-chlorophenyl group, will be slightly less than that on the *p*-bromophenyl group, and accordingly the paratonic ester (17; R = Cl) will be formed in a slightly greater proportion than the paraconic ester (17; R = Br).

Experimental

I.r. spectra (KBr discs) were measured on UR10 Zeiss Jena Universal Spectrophotometer, and u.v. spectra (in ethanol) on VSUI VEB Carl Zeiss Jena Universal Spectrophotometer.

Preparation of 6-aroyle tetralins: A cooled stirred mixture of the aroyl chloride (0.1 mole) and tetralin (0.3 mole) in carbon disulphide (200 ml) was treated portionwise with powdered anhydrous aluminium

General procedure for Stobbe condensation. A mixture of 6-aroyle tetralin (0.1 mole) and diethyl succinate (0.2 mole) in *t*-butyl alcohol (30 ml) was added during 20 min to a boiling stirred solution of potassium *t*-butoxide in *t*-butyl alcohol [from potassium (0.14g-atom) in *t*-butyl alcohol (30 ml per 1 g potassium)]. The heating was continued for a further 55 min and most of the alcohol was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was acidified, extracted with ether, and the ethereal solution was extracted with cold sodium carbonate solution. The alkaline extract, in the case of 6-*p*-tolyl tetralin was separated into two layers, (a) an upper, small, viscous and brownish black layer, [concentrated solution of sodium salt of the *trans*-(*p*-tolyl/CO₂Et)-half-ester (2; R¹ = Me)], and (b) a lower, pale yellow layer (sodium salt of succinic acid (0.6 g)). In the case of 6-*p*-chloro-, and 6-*p*-bromobenzoyl tetralin, the acids precipitated on acidification were triturated with *n*-hexane followed by addition of few milliliters of ether to leave a solid which was filtered off and identified as the *cis*-(*p*-R¹C₆H₄/CO₂Et)-half-esters (3; R¹ = Cl) and (3; R¹ = Br), respectively. Slow evaporation of the *n*-hexane-ether extract gave the *trans*-isomers (2; R¹ = Cl) and (2; R¹ = Br), respectively. The ratio of the *trans*-(2; R¹ = Cl) and *cis*-(3; R¹ = Cl)-half-esters was about 3 : 2, while that of the *trans*-(2;

TABLE 2. HALF-ESTERS 2 AND (3) AND DIBASIC ACIDS (8)

Compound	M.P. °C	Yield %	Found %			M.F.	Required %			γC = O/cm ⁻¹
			C	H	Hal.		C	H	Hal.	
2; R ¹ = Me	122-3(H-E≠)	80	75.9	6.9		C ₂₄ H ₂₆ O ₄	76.2	6.9		1710
8; R ¹ = Me	150-2(A)	91	75.0	6.7		C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₄	75.4	6.3		1710
2; R ¹ = Cl	126-7(H)	43.2	69.0	5.8	9.1	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₄ Cl	69.3	5.8	8.9	1703
8; R ¹ = Cl	175-7(A)	97	68.4	5.4	9.6	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₄ Cl	68.0	5.2	9.6	1695
3; R ¹ = Cl	171 (H)	28.8	68.6	5.9	9.4	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₄ Cl	69.3	5.8	8.9	1710
2; R ¹ = Br	125-7(H)	43	62.0	5.3	17.9	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₄ Br	62.3	5.2	18.0	1712
3; R ¹ = Br	185 (H)	22	62.1	4.8	17.8	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₄ Br	62.3	5.2	18.0	1712

* H = *n*-hexane, E = Ether, A = Acetic acid

$R^1 = Br$) and *cis*-(3; $R^1 = Br$)-half-esters was about 2:1. These ratios were also obtained spectrophotometrically according to the method of Dewar and Usher¹³ (mentioned later). The half-esters (2; $R^1 = Me$), (2 and 3; $R^1 = Cl$), (2 and 3; $R^1 = Br$) were recovered practically unchanged when refluxed with potassium *t*-butoxide in *t*-butanol. This indicated that no isomerisation occurred during the Stobbe condensation. The results are reported in Table 2.

Oxidation of the half-esters (2; $R^1 = Me$), (2 and 3; $R^1 = Cl$), and (2 and 3; $R^1 = Br$). A stirred solution of the half-esters (2.0 g) in 20% sodium carbonate solution was oxidised by portionwise addition of 2% potassium permanganate solution until the colour persisted (about 45 ml). The reaction mixture was left at room temperature for further 2 hr and worked up as usual. In each case, the neutral oxidation product proved to be the corresponding 6-aryol tetralin.

Saponification of the half-esters. The half-esters (2; $R^1 = Me$), and (2; $R^1 = Cl$) (4.0 g) were refluxed for 2-3 hr with 10% aqueous or alcoholic solution of potassium hydroxide (60 ml) and worked up as usual. The resulting products were crystallised from acetic acid to give the corresponding dibasic acids (8; $R^1 = Me$) and (8; $R^1 = Cl$). The results are reported in Table 2.

Cyclisation of the half-esters (2; $R^1 = Me$), (2 and 3; $R^1 = Cl$), and (2 and 3; $R^1 = Br$). A mixture of the half-ester (0.01 mole) and freshly fused sodium acetate (0.018 mole) was refluxed for 5 hr, and the neutral products (4a; $R^1 = Me$), (6a; $R^1 = Cl$), (6a; $R^1 = Br$) were isolated in the usual manner¹⁴ (cf. Table 3). The oily acetoxy-naphthoates (4a; $R^1 = Cl$) and (4a; $R^1 = Br$) were directly hydrolysed to their corresponding phenolic acids.

Hydrolysis of acetoxy-esters. (4a; $R^1 = Me$), (4a and 6a; $R^1 = Cl$), and (4b and 6b; $R^1 = Br$). This was accomplished by refluxing with 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (15 ml per gram of ester) for 3 hr to give the corresponding hydroxy-acids 4b and 6b respectively (cf. Table 3).

Methoxy-acids. (4d; $R^1 = Me$), (4d and 6d; $R^1 = Cl$), and (4d and 6d; $R^1 = Br$). A mixture of the acids (4b; $R^1 = Me$), (4b and 6b; $R^1 = Cl$), and (4b and 6b; $R^1 = Br$) (3.5 g), dimethyl sulphate (9.0 g) anhydrous potassium carbonate (12.0 g), and dry acetone (90 ml) was refluxed for 10 hr, and the neutral products were isolated as usual. The methoxy-esters were crystallised from the suitable solvents (cf. Table 3).

The methoxy-esters were hydrolysed to the corresponding acids (cf. Table 3) by refluxing for 3 hr with 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide (ca 20 ml per gram of ester).

Decarboxylation of the methoxy-acids (4d; $R^1 = Me$) and (4d and 6d; $R^1 = Cl$). The methoxy acid (3.5 g), copper bronze (1.0 g) and quinoline (30 ml) were refluxed for 3.5 hr in a current of dry nitrogen. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual to give

(4e; $R^1 = Me$) and (4e and 6e; $R^1 = Cl$), respectively (cf. Table 3).

Preparation of binaphthyl- and phenanthrene derivatives. The tetrahydro-derivatives (4e; $R^1 = Me$) and (4e and 6e; $R^1 = Cl$) (0.05 mole) were heated with selenium powder (1.0 g) at 300° for 12 hr and worked up as usual to give (5e; $R^1 = Me$) and (5e and 7e; $R^1 = Cl$), respectively (cf. Table 3).

4-Methoxy-1-(2'-naphthyl)-2-naphthoic acid (5d; $R^1 = H$) and *4-Methoxy-1-phenylphenanthrene-2-carboxylic acid* (7d; $R^1 = H$). These acids were prepared by the following two methods: (i) The methoxy-esters (4c and 6c; $R^1 = Cl$) and (4c and 6c; $R^1 = Br$) were mixed with dry 5% palladium-carbon catalyst (0.4 g) and heated to about 200° with frequent stirring for 3 hr. The reaction mixtures were cooled, dissolved in ether and filtered. The dry ethereal solution (Na_2SO_4) was evaporated and the residual oil solidified on trituration with *n*-hexane. They were crystallised from glacial acetic acid to give the corresponding naphthoic acids (5d; $R^1 = H$) and (7d; $R^1 = H$), m.p.s. 178° and 226°-7°, respectively; undepressed when admixed with authentic samples³ (cf. Table 3). (ii) The solution of the methoxy-esters (4c and 6c; $R^1 = Cl$ or Br) (4 g) in the least amount of tetralin (5 ml) was refluxed with dry palladium-carbon catalyst (5%) (1.0 g) for 2 hr, cooled and extracted with ether. The dry ethereal extract was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure, and the oily residue was refluxed with 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled, extracted with ether and the alkaline solution was acidified with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitated acids were crystallised from glacial acetic acid to give the naphthoic acids (5d and 7d; $R^1 = H$) (2.0 g), m.p.s. 178° and 226°-7°, respectively, identical with those obtained by the first method.

4-Methoxy-1,2'-binaphthyl (5e; $R^1 = H$). The methoxy-acid (5d; $R^1 = H$) (1.0 g) was decarboxylated with copper bronze (1.5 g) and quinoline (30 ml) in the usual manner. The product was worked up as usual to give (5e; $R^1 = H$), m.p. 166°. It has the same m.p. and electronic spectrum as those of an authentic specimen.³

Conversion of the dibasic acids (8; $R^1 = Me$) and (8; $R^1 = Cl$) into *oxo-indenylacetic acids* (10; $R^1 = Me$) and (10; $R^1 = Cl$). The dibasic acids (3.5 g) were refluxed for 2 hr with acetyl chloride (20 ml/gram of acid) to give the anhydrides (9; $R^1 = Me$) and (9; $R^1 = Cl$) which failed to solidify. Powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (ca 3.5 g) was added to the stirred ice-cold solution of the crude anhydride in dry nitrobenzene (30 ml) and stirring was continued for 4 hrs. The mixture was then left for 2 days at room temperature with occasional stirring and worked up as usual to give the oxoindenylacetic acids (10; $R^1 = Me$) and (10; $R^1 = Cl$) (cf. Table 5).

Cyclisation of the oxo-indenylacetic acids (10; $R^1 = Me$) and (10; $R^1 = Cl$). A mixture of the oxoindenylacetic acid (0.01 mole) and freshly fused sodium acetate (0.02 mole) in acetic anhydride (ca 40 ml/g of sodium acetate) was refluxed for 6 hr, and the

TABLE 3. TETRAHYDRO-1, 2'-BINAPHTHYS AND 4-ZAYLPHENANTHERENES

Compound	M.P. (°C) (solv.)	Yield %	Found %			Formula	Required %			Infrared spectra (cm ⁻¹)		
			C	H	Hal.		C	H	Hal	ν C = O	ν OH	γ Ar(H)
4a; R ¹ = Me	119-120(H)	100	77.2	6.9		C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₄	77.6	6.5		1765		
6a; R ¹ = Cl	141-142(H)	92	71.2	5.6	8.4	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₄ Cl	71.0	5.5	8.4	1712		
6a; R ¹ = Br	136-137(H)	96	64.0	4.8	17.1	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₄ Br	64.25	4.95	17.1	1757		
4b; R ¹ = Me	186-187(A)	95	79.6	6.5		C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₃	79.5	6.1		1702		
4b; R ¹ = Cl	140-142(A)	91	71.2	4.6	10.9	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₃ Cl	71.5	4.85	10.1	1760		3270*
6b; R ¹ = Cl	220-221(A)	97	71.4	5.0	10.9	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₃ Cl	71.5	4.85	10.1	1710		3200*
4b; R ¹ = Br	210-211(A)	95	63.5	4.5	19.8	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₃ Br	63.5	4.3	20.1	1695		3275*
6b; R ¹ = Br	230-232(A)	95	63.4	4.3	20.6	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₃ Br	63.5	4.3	20.	1690		3150*
4c; R ¹ = Me	87- 88(H)	95	79.6	6.5		C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₃	80.0	6.7		1710		
4c; R ¹ = Cl	150-151(M)	90	73.0	5.8	9.9	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₃ Cl	72.5	5.5	9.3	1725		
6c; R ¹ = Cl	151 (M)	90	72.9	5.6	9.2	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₃ Cl	72.5	5.5	9.3	1727		
4c; R ¹ = Br	153-155(M)	91	64.9	4.6	18.7	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₃ Br	64.95	5.0	18.8	1720		
6c; R ¹ = Br	160-161(M)	92	74.7	4.5	18.7	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₃ Br	64.95	5.0	18.8	1723		
4d; R ¹ = Me	221-222(A)	92	79.8	6.1		C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₃	79.7	6.4		1720		
4d; R ¹ = Cl	204-206(A)	98	71.6	5.2	9.5	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₃ Cl	72.3	5.2	9.7	1695		
6d; R ¹ = Cl	220-221(A)	95	72.0	5.2	9.4	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₃ Cl	72.0	5.2	9.7			
4e; R ¹ = Me	127-128(M)	70	87.5	7.5		C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O	87.4	7.3				825(2H) 895(1H)
4e; R ¹ = Cl	136-137(M)	93	77.9	6.0	10.7	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ OCl	78.1	5.9	11.0			825(2H) 890(1H) 820(2H)
6e; R ¹ = Cl	117-118(M)	90	78.2	5.9	11.0	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ OCl	78.1	5.9	11.0			
5e; R ¹ = Me	177-178(H)	60	88.4	6.0		C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O	88.7	6.1				
5e; R ¹ = Cl	180-181(H)	50	78.7	4.7	11.2	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ OCl	79.1	4.7	11.1			
7e; R ¹ = Cl	127-128(H)	50	79.1	5.1	11.1	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O Cl	79.1	4.7	11.1			
5d; R ¹ = H	178(B)	90										
7d; R ¹ = H	226-227(A)	90								1704		750(5H) 707
5e; R ¹ = H	166(P)	56										

H = *n*-Hexane, A = Acetic acid, M = Methanol, B = Benzene, P = Light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°C).

* = Broad band.

neutral brown cyclisation product was isolated in the usual manner to give the acetoxy-tetrahydro-13H-dibenzo [a, g] fluoren-13-ones (1a; R¹ = Me and Cl), respectively (cf. Table 5).

Tetrahydro-methoxy-13H-dibenzo-[a, g] fluoren-13-ones (11c; R¹ = Me and Cl). These were prepared by the following two methods: (i) The acetoxy-tetrahydro-dibenzo [a, g] fluorene-13-one (0.01 mole) (11a; R¹ = Me or Cl) was hydrolysed with 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide (50 ml) to give the corresponding tetrahydro-hydroxy-dibenzo [a, g]-fluoren-13-one (11b; R¹ = Me or Cl) (cf. Table 5). These

were methylated by refluxing for 12 hr with a mixture of dimethyl sulphate (9.0 g) anhydrous potassium carbonate (12.0 g) and dry acetone (ca 30 ml/g) fluorenone). The red products were crystallised from suitable solvents to give the tetrahydro-13H-dibenzo [a, g] fluoren-13-ones (11c; R¹ = Me and Cl, respectively) (cf. Table 5). (ii) The solution of the 1-(6-tetralyl)-2-naphthoic acids (4d; R¹ = Me or Cl) (1.8 g) in dry benzene (50 ml) was refluxed with phosphoric oxide (9.0 g) for 2 hr. The benzene was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was cooled and decomposed with water. The red product

was worked up as usual to give the above tetrahydro-13H-dibenzo [a, g]-fluoren-13-ones (11c; R¹ 4-Me or Cl) (cf. Table 5).

Evaluation of the relative proportion of the cis- and trans isomeric Half-esters by electronic spectroscopy. (i) *trans*-(*p*-Cl-C₆H₄/CO₂Et) (2; R¹ = Cl) to *cis*-(3; R¹ = Cl) half-esters: This ratio was determined spectrophotometrically in alcohol according to the method of Dewar and Urech.¹³ If C₁, and C₂, are the concentrations in g/litre of the pure half-esters (2; R¹ = Cl), and (3; R¹ = Cl), and E₁ and E₂ are their optical

densities respectively, then plotting E_{obs}/E₁ [E_{obs} = the optical density of the unknown binary mixture from Stobbe condensation product; containing x₁ g/litre of the *trans*-half-ester (2; R¹ = Cl) and x₂ g/litre of the *cis*-half-ester (3; R¹ = Cl)] at various wavelengths versus the corresponding values of E₂/E₁, gave a straight line of slope x₂/C₂ and the intercept on E_{obs}/E₁ axis = x₁/C₁ (cf. Fig. 1). From these two relations x₁ and x₂ were calculated. The results indicate that (2; R¹ = Cl) and (3; R¹ = Cl) are present in the mixture in the ratio 3:2, which is

FIG. 1

$$\frac{x_1}{C_1} = \frac{x_1}{0.0038} = 1 \quad ; \quad \text{then } x_1 = 0.0038 \text{ g}$$

$$\text{slope} = \frac{x_2}{C_2} = \frac{a \cdot b}{b \cdot c} = \frac{x_2}{0.0087} = \frac{2}{7} \quad ; \quad \text{then } x_2 = 0.0029 \text{ g}$$

FIG. 2

$$\frac{x_1}{C_1} = \frac{x_1}{0.012} = 0.5 \quad , \quad \text{then } x_1 = 0.0060 \text{ g}$$

$$\text{slope} = \frac{x_2}{C_2} = \frac{a \cdot b}{b \cdot c} = \frac{x_2}{0.005} = \frac{1}{3} \quad ; \quad \text{then } x_2 = 0.00173 \text{ g}$$

TABLE 4. ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF 1-TETRALYLNAPHTHALENES, 5, 6, 7, 8-TETRAHYDROPHENANTHRENES, BINAPHTHYLS AND PHENANTHRENES (IN ABSOLUTE ETHANOL)

Compound	1B_b (Band I)		1L_a (Band II)		1L_b (Band III)	
	$\lambda_{max/nm}$	ϵ	$\lambda_{max/nm}$	ϵ	$\lambda_{max/nm}$	ϵ
4a; R ¹ = Me	218.0 247.5	25,000 47,800	297.5	7,700	~330-345	1,440
6a; R ¹ = Cl	220.0 250.0	29,280 54,460	298.0	7,810	~340-345	1,640
6a; R ¹ = Br	222.0 252.0	23,760 41,580	300.0	9,030	~340-345	2,610
4b; R ¹ = Cl	250.0	35,400	315.0	6,130	obscured	
6b; R ¹ = Cl	245.0	36,160	312.0	8,140	345	5,400
4b; R ¹ = Br	222.0 255.0	26,100 36,750	315.0	8,250	obscured	
6b; R ¹ = Br	220.0 252.0	33,700 44,210	312.5	8,000	obscured	
4c; R ¹ = Me	222.0 252.0	30,150 36,500	308.0	8,100	340	4,770
4c; R ¹ = Cl	219.0 251.0	25,000 29,200	310.0	6,560	~330-335	5,310
6c; R ¹ = Cl	220.0 252.0	30,410 40,750	308.0	9,730	340.0	5,960
4d; R ¹ = Me	220.0 245.0	37,070 41,190	305.0	6,790	~330-335	2,570
4d; R ¹ = Cl	218.0 252.0	26,800 30,420	310.0	4,760	obscured	
6d; R ¹ = Cl	220.0 250.0	41,220 51,560	308.0	9,940	obscured	
4e; R ¹ = Me	217.0 240.0	36,600 27,560	297.0	9,360	~325-330	3,850
4e; R ¹ = Cl	215.0 245.0	32,450 25,890	303.0	8,780	325.0	7,640
6e; R ¹ = Cl	220.0 230.0	38,970 45,030	285.0 307.0	8,200 12,230	335.0	7,080
5e; R ¹ = Me	215.0 ~240-245	78,230 35,760	275.0 305.0	14,080 14,080	~330-335	8,270
5e; R ¹ = Cl	219.0 ~240-245	68,040 43,430	275.0 307.5	14,040 13,610	~330-335	8,690
7e; R ¹ = Cl	218.0 255.0	50,880 43,180	~270-275 ~300-305	24,450 12,310	340.0 360.0	3,080 2,050
7d; R ¹ = H	215.5 255.0	29,280 47,910	~270-275 ~300-310	27,280 9,410	342.0 360.0	2,600 2,600
5e; R ¹ = H	222.0 ~240-245	62,200 31,200	275.0 295.0	15,400 16,860	~320-325	10,980
~ Inflexion						

TABLE 5. THE TETRAHYDRO-OKO-INDENYLACETIC ACIDS (10) AND TETRAHYDRO-13H-DIBENZO [a, g] FLUOREN-13-ONES (11)

Compound	M.P. (°C) (Solv.)	Yield %	Found %			Formula	Required %			Infrared spectra (cm ⁻¹)		
			C	H	Hal.		C	H	Hal.	νC=O	νOH	γAr(H)
10; R ¹ = Me D.N.P.	188.9 (P) ^a 175.6 (Et)	90	79.1 N = 11.5	6.1		C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₃ C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₄	79.5 N = 10.9	6.1		1717		845(2H)
10; R ¹ = Cl D.N.P.	222.4 (B-H) 223.5(Et)	80	71.2 N = 10.5	5.2	11.6	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₃ Cl C ₂₇ H ₂₁ O ₆ ClN ₄	71.5 N = 10.5	4.85	10.1	1720 1703		845(2H)
11a; R ¹ = Me D.N.P.	139.40(H-E) 297.8 (Et)	70	81.3 N = 10.7	5.9		C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₃ C ₃₁ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₄	80.9 N = 10.4	5.7		1765 1710		
11a; R ¹ = Cl D.N.P.	190.1 (H-E) 278.80(Et)	71	73.5 N = 10.6	4.4	9.4	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₃ Cl C ₂₉ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₄ Cl	73.3 N = 10.1	4.55	9.4	1772 1710		
11b; R ¹ = Me D.N.P.	254.5 (Et) 292(B)	50	84.4 N = 11.1	5.3		C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₂ C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₅ N ₄	84.1 N = 11.3	5.8		1705	3360	
11b; R ¹ = Cl D.N.P.	260.3 (Et) 292(B)	90	75.5 N = 10.6	4.7	10.3	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₂ Cl C ₂₇ H ₁₉ O ₅ ClN ₄	75.3 N = 10.9	4.5	10.6	1695	3385	
11c; R ¹ = Me D.N.P.	242.3 (B) 273.5 (B)	90	83.9 N = 10.6	5.8		C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₂ C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₄	84.1 N = 11.0	6.1		1700		
11c; R ¹ = Cl D.N.P.	221-223(B) 267.8 (B)	86	75.7 N = 10.4	4.6	10.4	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ Cl C ₂₈ H ₂₁ O ₅ ClN ₄	75.8 N = 10.6	4.9	10.2	1708		

^aP = Light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°), B = Benzene, H = *n*-Hexane, Et = Ethanol, E = Ether

TABLE 6. ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF THE OKO-INDENYLACETIC ACIDS (10) AND 1, 2, 3, 4-TETRAHYDRO-13-H-DIBENZO [a, g] FLUOREN-13-ONES (11) IN ABSOLUTE ETHANOL

Compound	¹ B ₂ (Band I)		¹ L _a (Band II)		¹ L _b (Band III)		<i>n</i> → <i>n</i> * band (R-band)	
	λ _{max} /nm	ε	λ _{max} /nm	ε	λ _{max} /nm	ε	λ _{max} /nm	ε
10; R ¹ = Me	250	40,440	302.5	9,060	obscured		430	1,440
10; R ¹ = Cl	250	30,690	287.5	8,800	335	3,510	414	900
11c; R ¹ = Me	225	29,510	275.0 305.0	34,470 30,030	obscured		490	790
11c; R ¹ = Cl	220	28,410	275.0 300.0	47,140 28,100	335	6,410	400-410 480	510 1,010

nearly the same ratio obtained experimentally by fractional crystallisation.

(ii) *Trans*-(*p*-Br-C₆H₄/CO₂Et)(2; R¹ = Br) to *cis*-(3; R¹ = Br) *half-esters*: This ratio was determined by the same method as mentioned above (cf. Fig 2). The results indicate that (2; R¹ = Br) and (3; R¹ = Br) are present in the ratio 2:1, which is nearly the same ratio obtained experimentally by fractional crystallisation.

References

- PART VII, F. G. BADDAR, M. N. BASYOANI, M. F. EL-NEWAIHY, and E. H. GHALY *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974.
- L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", John Wiley, Second Edition, 1966, p. 65.
- F. G. BADDAR, W. AWAD, F. A. FOULI, S. A. OMRAN and M. I. B. SELIM, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1968, 507.
- A. D. CAMPBELL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3659.
- L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", John Wiley, Second edition, 1966, (a) p. 162; (b) p. 132.
- A. STREITWIESER (JR.), "Molecular Orbital Theory for Organic Chemists", Wiley, New York, 1961, p. 169.
- L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", John Wiley, Second edition, 1966, p. 149; and F. G. BADDAR, S. SHERIF, L. EKLADIOS and A. EL-AZIZ AZAB, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1967, 506.
- F. G. BADDAR, M. F. EL-NEWAIHY and R. O. LOUTFY, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1970, 620.
- W. S. JOHNSON, A. L. McCLOSKEY, and D. A. DUNNIGAN, *J. Amer Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 514.
- JERRY MARCH, "Advanced Organic Chemistry, Reactions and Structure", McGraw-Hill Book Company, New York, 1968, p. 147.
- CRAM, "Fundamentals of Carbanion Chemistry", Academic Press Inc., New York, 1965, p. 85.
- J. ROBERTS and M. CASERIO, "Basic Principles of Organic Chemistry", Benjamin, Inc., New York, 1964, p. 370.
- M. J. S. DEWAR and D. S. URCH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 345.
- F. G. BADDAR, L. S. EL-ASSAL and V. B. BAGHOS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 1714; 1958, 986.